

SUGGESTED MODEL FOR IMPLEMENTING B.ED. SEMESTER SYSTEM

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Introduction

“No innovation or change can be implemented without proper planning, teacher’s awareness, involvement, and commitment”.

B.Ed. is professional course catering mainly to the needs of prospective secondary teachers. In the view of modern development and trends in teacher education U.G.C. has taken decision to introduce the semester and choice based credit system in all central, state and deemed universities under the eleventh five year plan. Many universities already started semester based credit point system. To implement semester based credit point system, the scheme of organization of courses and practical work of B.Ed. programme need revision.

This paper attempts to present “A suggested model to implement B.Ed. programme for semester system.

Objectives:

1. To introduce element of diversification in the implementation of semester based credit point system in B.Ed. course.
2. To suggest scheme of examination and instructional hours.

Duration of the course:

The duration of bachelor of education (B.Ed.) shall be one academic year, comprising of two semester i.e July to November and December to April/May. As per U.G.C.and N.C.T.E. there will be teaching / instruction of 90 days in a semester comprising 18 weeks in a year

A candidate has to attend a minimum of two semesters of 18 weeks, each covering 10 theory course and practical work as given below.

SEMESTER SCHEME

(Diagrammatic presentation)

First semester (18 weeks)				Second semester (18 weeks)					
1 st July 2012 TO 30 th November 2012				1 st December2012 TO 30 th April 2013					
Block A	Block B	Block C	BlockD		BlockA	Block B	Block C	Block D	13 th
6 weeks	5 weeks	6 weeks	1 weeks		6 weeks	5 weeks	6 weeks	1 weeks	Apr
1 st July12 to 12 th Aug 12	13 th Aug12 To 16 Sept 12	17 th Sept 12 TO 28 TH Oct 12	*29 th Oct 12 To 5 th Nov12	*6 th Nov12 to 30 th Nov 12	1 st Dec12 To 20 Th Jan 13	21 st Jan 13 To 24 th Feb 13	25 th Feb 13 To 7 th Apr 13	8 th Apr13 To 13 TH April 13	30 th Apr il 13* *
Lecture s + Practic al work	Practice Teachin g	Lecture s + Practic al work	First semester Examinat ion	Vacatio n, Assessm ent. result	Lecture s + Practica l work	Practic eTeac hing	Lectur es + Practic al work	Secon d semest er Exami nation	Ass esm ent , Res ult

***These dates may change as per Diwali vacation**

**** May and June- Summer vacation and admission procedure.**

FIRST SEMESTER

1st July 2012 TO 30th November 2012 (18 weeks)

BLOCK A

1st July 2012 to 12th August 2012

Morning Session

Time: 10.00 am. To 2.00 pm.

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
1.Philosophical Foundation of Education	5	30 Hrs.
2.Psychology of the Learner	5	30 Hrs.
3.Educational Evaluation	5	30 Hrs.
4.Information and Communication Technology in Education	5	30 Hrs.
5.Method - I	5	30 Hrs.
TOTAL		150 Hrs.

Afternoon Session

Time: 2.30 pm To 4.30 pm

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
Micro Teaching (Concept, Demonstration, Lesson Planning, Microteaching)	8 Hrs/week (5 weeks)	40 Hrs
Preparation and use of instructional material (teaching aids)	2.5 Hrs/ week	15 Hrs +2 Hrs =17 Hrs
Simulated lessons(Two) (Concept, Demonstration, Lesson Planning, Teaching)	2.5 Hrs/ week	15 Hrs
TOTAL		72 Hrs.

BLOCK -B

13th August 2012 to 16th September 2012 (5 weeks)

PRACTICE TEACHING (MACRO TEACHING)

DAY	1	2	3	4	5	6
WEEK	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
First	Concept of lesson planning/practice teaching, Steps of lesson plan, Detail discussion. Observation Book	Demonstration lessons (Four) 2- teacher Educator 2-Past Students With detail discussion	Lesson planning work shop Preparation of minimum 5 lesson plans /lesson Guidance under supervision	Lesson planning work shop Preparation of minimum 5 lesson plans /lesson Guidance under supervision	Practice Teaching in Schools Observation of 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator.	Practice Teaching in Schools Observation of 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator.
Second	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Practice Teaching Lesson planning and Guidance	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Practice Teaching Lesson planning and Guidance
Third	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-
Fourth	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-
Fifth	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-

FIVE WEEKS = 30 Days = 12 DAYS Lesson Planning and Guidance +18 Days Actual Practice Teaching

Practice Teaching – 18 Days x 8 lessons x 7 Teacher Educator

= 1000 lessons (In First semester We have to complete 100 students x 10 Lessons)

BLOCK C

17th September 2012 to 28th October 2012 (6 Weeks)

Morning Session

Time: 10.00 am. To 2.00 pm.

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
1.Philosophical Foundation of Education	5	30 Hrs.
2.Psychology of the Learner	5	30 Hrs.
3.Educational Evaluation	5	30 Hrs.
4.Information and Communication Technology in Education	5	30 Hrs.
5.Method – I	5	30 Hrs.
TOTAL		150 Hrs.

Afternoon Session

Time: 2.30 pm To 4.30 pm

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
Seminar	2 Hrs/ week	12 Hrs
Open Book Assignment	1 Hrs/week	6 Hrs
Content Test	1 Hrs/week	6 Hrs
Essays(Five)	2 Hrs/ week	12 Hrs
Unit planning /Unit Test preparation only	2 Hrs/ week	10 Hrs

Co-curricular Activity	2 Hrs/ week	11 Hrs
Class Test	3 Hrs/ week	15 Hrs
TOTAL		72 Hrs

BLOCK D

29th October 12 To 5th November2012 (one week)

Second Semester Examination

6th Nov2012 to 30th Nov 2012

Vacation, Assessment. Announcement of result

SECOND SEMESTER

1st December 2012 to 30th April 2013 (18 weeks)

BLOCK A

1st December 2012 to 20th January2013 (6 –weeks)

Morning Session

Time: 10.00 am. To 2.00 pm.

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
6.Sociological Foundation of Education	5	30 Hrs.
7.Psychology of the Learning	5	30 Hrs.
8.Educational Management	5	30 Hrs.
9.special fields/optional subjects	5	30 Hrs.
10.Method – II	5	30 Hrs.
TOTAL		150 Hrs.

Afternoon Session

Time: 2.30 pm To 4.30 pm

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
CAI (Concept, Demonstration, Lesson Planning, Teaching)	5 Hrs/week	30 Hrs
Individual Project	4 Hrs/ week	24 Hrs
Simulated lessons(Two) (Concept, Demonstration, Lesson Planning, Teaching)	2.5 Hrs/ week	15 Hrs
Essays(one)	0.5 Hrs/week	3 Hrs
TOTAL		72 Hrs.

BLOCK -B

21st January 2013 to 24th February 2013 (5 weeks)

PRACTICE TEACHING (MACRO TEACHING)

DAY	1	2	3	4	5	6
WEEK	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
First	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Practice Teaching Lesson planning and Guidance	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	Practice Teaching Lesson planning and Guidance.
Second	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-

Third	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-
Fourth	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator
Fifth	Practice Teaching Lesson planning and Guidance	-do-	Lesson Observation 8- lessons per day by Teacher Educator	-do-	-do-	-do-

FIVE WEEKS = 30 Days = 8 DAYS Lesson Planning and Guidance +22 Days Actual Practice Teaching

Practice Teaching – 22 Days x 8 lessons x 7 Teacher Educator = 1232 lessons*

((In second semester we have to complete 100 students x 10 Lessons = 1000 Lessons)

*Additional four days (232 Lessons) to be utilized to complete remaining lessons.

BLOCK C

25th February 2013 to 7th April 2013 (6 –weeks)

Morning Session

Time: 10.00 am. To 2.00 pm.

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
6.Sociological Foundation of Education	5	30 Hrs.
7.Psychology of the Learning	5	30 Hrs.
8.Educational Management	5	30 Hrs.
9.special fields/optional subjects	5	30 Hrs.

10.Method – II	5	30 Hrs.
TOTAL		150 Hrs.

Afternoon Session

Time: 2.30 pm To 4.30 pm

COURSE	HOURS/WEEK	TOTAL
Community Work	4 Hrs/ week	24 Hrs
Internship	4 Hrs/ week	24 Hrs + 1Hrs =25 Hrs
Essays(four)	2 Hrs/week (four weeks)	8Hrs
Class Test	3 Hrs/ week(five weeks)	15 Hrs
TOTAL		72 Hrs.

BLOCK D

8th April 2013 To 13th April 2013 (one week)

Second Semester Examination

13th April 2013 to 30th April 2013

Assessment and announcement of result

Quality of schools are solely depends on the quality of teacher education. To impart effective teacher education effective planning is necessary .if we utilized maximum time allotted for each course then it will be beneficial for student teachers empowerment. it will improve the quality of teacher education.so so there is urgent need to implementation and planning of the semester based credit point system

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